

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice

9 & 10 September 2024 | Manchester

Key reflections

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice conference, 9-10 September 2024

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The bullet points below represent *key reflections* and messages from the presentations at the *Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice 2025 conference*. This took place on 9th & 10th September 2024 in Manchester. The event was hosted by the [AI for Multiple Long-Term Conditions Research Support Facility \(AIM RSF\)](#).

The AIM programme: Context, realisation and impact

- Meaningful engagement between researchers and people with Multiple Long-Term Conditions (MLTC) to shape the research is a crucial ingredient to ensure impact through including the representing the patient voice in the design, development and delivery of the AI work
- Early career researchers (ECRs) have enabled the development of educational training to support Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE)
- Collaboration is key: for example, collaboration with the SAIL databank in Swansea supported researchers, through the development of a JupyterHub solution, to deploy capability, unlocking the potential of novel and cutting-edge data science methods
- Skills in reproducibility and open science are hard to motivate, while teams lack access to data

- Project delivery plans, which are defined before funding is awarded, often make it difficult — though not impossible — to adjust activities later on. If real impact is the goal, funders should allow greater flexibility and agility throughout the project.
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- Ethical and regulatory considerations are almost impossible to define without already analysing the data - leading to the need for iterative development, which is not incentivised by the current academic reward system

Celebrating and recognising excellence in Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE)

- Over **150 patient & public members** are involved in the eight research collaboratives
- PPIE has helped to bridge the gap between expert knowledge and public understanding
- PPIE through representation of diverse groups who have previously been underrepresented contributes to research that can be trusted and effectively deployed into real-world healthcare settings
- PPIE contributors with intellectual disability care about fairness and ethical issues in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and how technology can support them
- Experienced clinicians can help support communication barriers and breakdown abstract concepts using non-verbal communication methods
- People with learning disability (PWLD) can and want to be included in AI discussions if given the right support, and creative approaches are used to aid understanding

Leveraging the UK's unique health data assets to catalyse AI research in MLTC

- Datasets across the UK are characterised by metadata listings, but there is not always all the relevant information needed for initial informed decisions
- There are complex matters to tie into funding and programme management (data access pathways, data use permutations, computational environments, data formats, cost, general sustainability)
- Standardisation of methodology and code sets for MLTC research is developing, but not yet wholly accessible
- Teams are promoting consortia publications, research outputs, and enhancing collaboration in maximising the potential of data in MLTC research
- Publish options for computational setups optimal for machine learning, AI, and general epidemiology
- There is a need to provide end-to-end support mechanisms for research consortia in using large-scale, complex data in MLTC research and beyond
- Routine health data is an imperfect record of what happened (exactly what, exactly when?)

- In MLTC research, there are too many conditions to use great precision, tend to revert to off-the-shelf code lists
- There are important choices about granular versus coarse data, including rules for overlaps
- Balancing data governance needs and research needs required “*workarounds*”: split protocols, phased approvals and linking protocols together to ensure same dataset could be used
- To support collaborative working involving different institutions, multi-study licences signed with individual institutions and where researchers across two institutions need to access data, third-party agreements are put in place
- Facilitating synthetic data access enables researchers to get a head start on understanding the data and start scripting analysis code in parallel with contracting and RDG approval processes
- Launching teaching licence based on Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) synthetic data, making access to synthetic CPRD datasets free

Scaling up the impact: Bridging the gap between research, policy, people and practice

- MLTC research should widen its lens from the frame of a biomedical model to include a greater social and behavioural focus – looking at disease clusters has its limitations
- New models of MLTC care are needed to shift the system from a fragmented, reactive one to one that is co-ordinated and patient-centred
- Research/evidence gaps need to be addressed, including how best to prevent the development of MLTC, how we equip the health workforce with the right blend of specialist and generalist skills and how to maximise benefits and limit the risk of treatment for patients with MLTC
- MLTC research should consider the social context as well as clinical parameters and the biomedical model
- Cluster-AIM study found that 40% of people with MLTC had a social care need that was not being met, and this is likely to be an under-estimate
- How can we quantify social care need in people in MLTC and develop clusters based on this?
- Policymakers are influenced by the “so what?” question in context of existing policy and to consider any influence on policy
- Policymakers want to know how findings link to policy and the wider/current context
- Highlight limitations, include caveats and explain uncertainties within the narrative of why the research matters
- If we use data-driven cluster analysis research to drive policy, we are missing part of the story - consider qualitative evidence as well
- The experience of living with MLTC is complex, multifaceted and often involves a great deal of work for the people affected
- Themes of work are not static for individuals; they ebb and flow and are personal to the people concerned and their context

- We need to work with people living with MLTC to understand the best way to capture this work in data using AI and other methods
- We should consider what constitutes evidence, which evidence informs policy and how
- There is potential to bring greater humanity to data-driven MLTC studies and policy
- Perhaps codes for social care needs should be introduced
- Care co-ordinators can help to get to the root of why people are hospitalised, considering social influences

Using real-world data to identify and plan interventions to minimise polypharmacy and transform prescribing in MLTC

- Many clinicians are sceptical about the use of AI (particularly when it comes to suggested actions)
- Most favour gold standard authoritative sources instead (BNF, NICE, etc.)
- Some clinicians see AI as a potential burden though most see some benefit in using AI
- Nearly all agreed that the use of AI needs to be transparent and supported by authoritative sources whenever possible
- Exploring the burden of polypharmacy presents many challenges, including the diversity of reasons intervals between prescriptions may exist, uncertainty in prescription stop date, dealing with big datasets and no access to secondary care prescriptions
- CPRD data can be used as a starting point for predictions about polypharmacy
- Analysis of individual drugs and total polypharmacy burden can illuminate better medicine plans for patients
- In developing a foundation health prediction model, AI did not work very well so automation is now being tried
- Progressing some population-level tools, combination methods and building a surveillance tool

Pushing at the boundaries: Can AI, data science & digital innovation transform MLTC in health and social care research

- Predictive modelling is central to the success of factors such as better internal decision-making, better regulations and better manufacturing processes
- Making good use of what we already know is the way forward in terms of drug development
- There are many problems with risk prediction and causal methods in a MLTC context and so a long way to go
- Whilst there is a great deal of hope and expectation around the use of AI in healthcare, this ambition should contextualise the current realities and limitations

- Need to address under-representation in healthcare data – which could be addressed by causal inference
- Challenges in causal AI that need to be addressed include large-scale discovery, causal representation, identifying what predictors really are and causal reasoning for decision support
- We need to understand AI more than we do today – and be able to explain it
- Explainability matters for effective engagement with the PPIE community
- Research funders could benefit from AI training to ask the right questions when research proposals include AI
- Trusted Research Environments (TREs) also need to be trained about AI – because AI models can be disclosive when released
- Collaboration between the AI developer and the TRE is important to understand whether an AI model is disclosive
- AI-ready datasets are the future but further definition is needed on what this means
- TREs and AI developers could collaborate more to help developers along the journey and speed up the science